

COMPARATIVE -TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER CATEGORY OF NOUNS IN UZBEK , RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

this article analyzes and compares the gender category of nouns in Uzbek, Russian and English languages with examples.

The word “*gender*” has been used since the 14th century as a grammatical term, referring to classes of noun as masculine, feminine, or neuter groups.

Grammatical gender is a formal category, but it does not refer to the biological difference between a man and a woman; rather it is an integral part of the linguistic system and it also includes inanimate entities. This system is used in approximately one quarter of the world’s languages. In 257 languages from different geographical areas and linguistic families, 112 are shown to have a gender system. In addition, the category of gender exists in Russian and it's represented by a system of three-member opposition: The category of gender is clearly observed in the singular forms.

Gender distinctions in the plural forms are considerably obliterated.

Masculine nouns include:

1) nouns which have stems ending in a hard consonant and a zero morpheme in the nominative case: **стол(stol)**;

For example: *Она забыла свою книгу на столе.*

After returning home she put down her hands on the table.

Stol ustida ruchka bor edi.

2) the majority of nouns which have stems ending in a softened consonant and in **-й, герой (qahramon)**;

For example: *Он был уникальным героем в этом городе.*

He killed a dragon as a result he was a hero in that city.

"Oybek domla o'z davrining qahramoni edi". (S. Ahmad, "Yo'qotganlarim va topganlarim")

3) nouns denoting male sex: **дядя (amaki, tog'a)**;

For example: *Он мой старший дядя. Мне очень нравится его персонаж.*

His uncle always cares his new house when he went to work.

Gulsum **amakising** oldiga har kuni ovqat olib borar edi.

4) nouns with the argumentative suffixes **-ище**, derived from the stem of masculine nouns:

домище, дом, (уу);

For example: *Этот **домище** очень красивый. Она сказала это своей матери.*

John said: "That **house** was very big".

*O'zingni yaxshi odamlarga yaqin tut, o'z **uyingdagi** ishlarga mashg'ul bo'l.*

5) nouns with the suffixes **-ишка** derived from the stem of masculine nouns: **шалунишка (shumtaka).**

For example: *Там **шалунишки** приложили уши к двери и прислушались.*

*He is very **playful** with girls however; he never makes upset them.*

Shumtaka bolalar eshikka quloq tutib gap poylashar edi.

Feminine nouns comprise:

1) an absolute majority of nouns with the ending **-а (я)** in the nominative case of the singular:

парта, сестра, (ора) земля, (уер);

For example: *Моя **сестра** любит готовить еду.*

*We have to protect our **Earth** from harmful situations.*

*"Agar sizga **yer** torlik qilib, yuragingiz yukni ko'tara olmay siqilsa, hayqiring".*

2) some nouns with a stem ending in a softened consonant excepting **-(й): тень(soya), сеть(to'r), ночь(tun).**

For example: *Вдруг она испугалась от своей **тени**.*

*Everyday he used **network** with his friends at school.*

Tunda Qosim Zubaydaning eshigini taqillatdi.

Neuter nouns include:

1) nouns with the ending **-о(е): окно;**

For example, *:Открой **окно**, сказал мне учитель! (Майя Кучерская "Тетя Мотя")*

*Linda opens **the window** during the rain.*

Har kuni ertalab Zumrad oynalarni ochib qo'yardi.

2) nouns ending in **-мя: время;**

For example: *Мы должны экономить наше **время** от ненужных вещей.*

*We spend **our time** in a proper way.*

*Qahhor **vaqtini** kun bo'yi telefon o'ynash bilan o'tkazdi.*

3) some of the undecidable inanimate nouns: **пальто.**

For example: *Я люблю это **пальто**. Я хочу купить это.*

*My mother's **coat** is very old. I need to purchase another one.*

*Menga bu **palto** yoqdi.*

Rendering of English nouns denoting male sex in Uzbek and Russian: English (father) Uzbek (ota), Russian (отец):

*"What an excellent **father** you have, girls" said she, when the door was shut (J. Austen "Pride and Prejudice").*

Otamizning o'lganiga ancha yil o'tib ketdi. (G'. Gulom "Mening o'g'rigina bolam").

*"Благословил меня **отец**" (А. С. Пушкин Евгений Онегин).*

English	Uzbek	Russian
uncle	amaki, tog'a	дядя

"I think I have heard you say that their uncle is an attorney on Meryton" (J. Austen "Pride and Prejudice").

Mirahmad amakining uyida suhbatlashib o'tirishar edi (Oybek "Bolaning ko'ngli poshsho").

Дядя милый и родной, с днем рожденья, дорогой! ("Дядя Ваня" Кучова Алиса)

English	Uzbek	Russian
lion	sher	лев

The lion shifters want to me ("Lion pride" Lilly Wilder).

Собачка поджала хвост и прижалась в угол клетки. Лев подошёл к ней и понюхал её ("Лев и собачка" Лев Толстой).

Sher u bilan qalin do'st bo'lib qoldi ("Sher va sichqon" O'zbek xalq maqoli).

Rendering of English nouns denoting female sex in Uzbek and Russian:

English	Uzbek	Russian
mother	ona	мама

Her sisters were uneasy for her, but her mother was delighted (J. Austen "Pride and Prejudice").

Мама спит, и я молчу ("Мама спит, она устала" Е.Благинина).

Jannat onalar oyog'i ostidadir (Maqol).

English	Uzbek	Russian
aunt	amma,xola	тетя

Do let the portraits of your uncle and aunt Philips be placed in the gallery at Pemberly? (J. Austen "Pride and Prejudice")

Тетя Мотя оставляет его досыпать (Майя Кучерская "Тетя Мотя").

Bashor xola bor ovozi bilan uni chaqirdi (O' Hoshimov "Ikki eshik orasi").

English	Uzbek	Russian
lioness	urg'ochi sher	львица

The lioness cares her cubs ("The lioness" Chris Bohjalian).

Chotqol qo'riqxonasida o'nlab urg'ochi sherlar bor (O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi).

Львица, обнаружив своего детеныша мертвым, долго горевала, оплакивала его и проклинала вола (Азиатские сказки).

From the examples above, we can come to the conclusion that the gender category of nouns can be expressed differently. Russian language follows more strictly its own rules of gender category of nouns than Uzbek and English.

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